

CONTROL OF SNAP-THROUGH PHENOMENON FOR THERMALLY DEFORMED CFRP LAMINATES WITH SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY WIRES

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SUMMARY: General anti-symmetric laminates deform into a cylindrical shape after cure processing due to the anisotropy of the coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE). This deformed plate exhibits a snap-through phenomenon. Although this deformation and the snap-through phenomenon are not desirable in general, such a system may be utilized as a smart structure by taking advantage of this feature. The present paper describes how we tried to control this snap-through by using Ti-Ni shape memory alloy straight wires.

KEY WORDS: CFRP, Anti-symmetric laminate, Thermal deformation, Snap-through phenomenon, Snap-through control by shape memory alloy.

INTRODUCTION

It is well-known that a laminated plate deforms with a temperature change from cure- to room-temperature unless the stacking sequence is symmetric. For example, Hyer [1] discussed this subject mainly from a phenomenological point of view. He showed the deformed shape was almost cylindrical as schematically shown in Fig.1, rather than a saddle-shaped deformation which is predicted by the small deflection theory.

For $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ crossply laminates, detailed analyses on the radius of curvature of the cylindrical shape and the bifurcation (snap-through) phenomenon have been conducted by many researchers [2-5] and theoretical understanding was almost completed by means of the large deformation theory.

The main purpose of this paper is to control the above mentioned snap-through phenomenon by using wires made of a shape memory alloy. If we push the center of the cylindrical-shaped panel, the panel deforms to another stable shape. Ideally, this can be done by the aid of the recovery force of the shape memory alloy. If this is realized under total control, the system may become a candidate for actuators, although it is not clear at this moment how this system could be used in practice.

Fig.1 Snap-through phenomenon of CFRP laminates.

In our previous paper [6], an attempt was made to control the snap-through phenomenon of CFRP laminates as shown in Fig.2 (a). The system of generating the snap-through consisted of CFRP laminates where a pair of SMA coils was attached on both the top and bottom surfaces with a pair of hooks. However, this system was voluminous and was not practicable. Therefore, we tried to downsize the control system of snap-through as the major motivation of this study. For this purpose, we tried to use straight SMA wires instead of the SMA coil springs.

Figure 2 (b) also shows a bygone snap-through control system with several SMA wires. The SMA wires were directly attached to the CFRP laminates by using a thread. If the curved SMA wires are heated, they tend to become straight and generate a bending load to the laminate which eventually caused the snap-through on. However, this system requires a number of SMA wires to generate the snap-through of even thin laminates such as $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_T$ laminates.

In the present study, we tried to control the snap-through phenomenon of CFRP laminates by only one SMA wire and a round bar as shown in Fig.2 (c). By inserting the round bar, the room-temperature curvature of the SMA wire becomes large and therefore, a large recovery force is expected when the SMA wire is heated.

SNAP-THROUGH CONTROL DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

To realize the above idea, we conducted the following three tasks: (1) fabrication of anti-symmetric laminates, (2) a 3-point bending test of SMA wire, (3) measurement of loads required for generating the snap-through. Task (2) is to find the recovery force of the SMA wire. If this recovery force exceeds the load measured by Task (3), the snap-through is expected to take place.

Fabrication and measurement of deflection

Unidirectional prepreps were cut into a square of 100×100 mm and stacked in a manner of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ or $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ as shown in Fig.1. The CFRP plates were fabricated on a flat plate where the curing temperature was 180°C . Then the thermal deformation at room temperature, w , was measured using a laser-type non-contact displacement transducer and the data were sent to a personal computer for further analysis.

3-point bending test of SMA wire

The memorized shape of the Ti-Ni shape memory alloy wire used in this experiment is straight and the diameter of the SMA wires is 1 mm.

(a) Snap-through control system with SMA coil.

(b) Snap-through control system with three SMA wires.

(c) Snap-through control system with one SMA wire and round bar.

Fig.2 Snap-through control systems.

Figure 3 schematically shows the 3-point bending test for the SMA wire. The distance between the support points is 100 mm, the same as the length and width of the laminates. By supplying an electric current, the temperature of the SMA wire increased due to the Joule heating and hence the recovery force was generated. The temperature of the Joule heating was measured by a T-thermocouple (Copper-Constantan). In the present system, the laminate and the SMA wire were originally curved and they gradually became straight. Therefore, we measured the recovery force of the SMA wire during the unloading in Fig.3.

Measurement of load required for snap-through

Figure 4 depicts the experimental image for the measurement of the load. To measure the necessary load to cause the snap-through, the pressure bar was pushed down at the center of the laminates until

Fig.3 3-point bending test of SMA wire.

Fig.4 Measurement of load required for snap-through phenomenon.

the snap-through took place. In this test, the cylindrical shaped laminate, Fig.1(a), was transformed into the other shape of Fig.1(b), immediately after becoming flat. We measured the load and the center displacement until the laminates underwent the snap-through phenomenon.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recovery force of SMA wire

Figure 5 is the result of the recovery force of the SMA wire versus the displacement at each temperature. As was already described, data were taken at the unloading stage, that is, in the direction from large displacement to zero displacement of Fig.5. At 30°C, some amount of deflection remained even after the SMA wire became load-free. If the temperature of the SMA wire was increased to more than 35°C, the SMA wire completely returned to the original straight line. In addition, the marks for 50°C, 60°C and 65°C all overlapped, whereas the recovery force depended on the temperature until 50°C. Thus, it was concluded that the characteristics of the SMA wire saturated at 50°C.

Figure 6 shows the skin stress-skin strain curves which are mere conversion of Fig.5.

In the present study, the strain of the SMA wire was below 1%. It is commonly recognized that Ti-Ni alloy has superior fatigue properties, that is, the SMA wire can bear 10^6 times' cyclic loads under the strain of 3%. Therefore, the recovery force of the SMA wire may not decrease in the range of the present study.

Table 1 shows Young's moduli of the SMA wires at 50°C, 60°C and 65°C. By using these Young's moduli, we will later make a comparison between the recovery force of the SMA wire and the load required for the snap-through in regard to the control of the snap-through.

Load required for snap-through

Figure 7 is a typical result of the load versus the displacement for the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ crossply laminates. First, the load and the displacement increased proportionally, and then the load suddenly decreased from 0.88 N to 0.54 N. At this point, the snap-through took place on only the half side of the cylindrical laminate, probably due to the pressure bar being shifted from the center of the laminate for some unknown reason. Finally, the complete snap-through took place when the displacement became 14 mm.

Figure 8 is the result of the $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ crossply laminates which are twice as thick as $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$. The required load was more than twice of the result of Fig.7.

The cured laminates did not necessarily exhibit a unique configuration. The radius of curvature, or equivalently, the initial height of laminates differed each other. Figure 9 shows the result of the required load to cause the snap-through versus the initial height of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminates. The load and the initial height of the laminates exhibited a linear correlation.

Control of snap-through by SMA wire

The present snap-through control system has an advantage of being able to adjust the load necessary for the snap-through by using a different size of round bars. We predicted the most suitable diameter of round bars for each laminate by comparing the recovery force of the SMA wire with the load required for the snap-through. Also, we confirmed whether or not these systems might actually show the snap-through.

Two kinds of charts, the recovery force of the SMA wire and the load required for the

Fig.7 Load required for snap-through, $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminate.

Fig.8 Load required for snap-through, $(0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2)$ laminate.

Fig.9 Required load to cause snap-through vs. initial height of $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminates.

snap-through, can be combined into one graph by the following equation:

$$P_{SMA} = \frac{48EI}{L^3} (h_0 + \phi - \delta_{CFRP}) \quad (1)$$

where P_{SMA} is the recovery force of SMA wire, E is Young's modulus of SMA wire, I is the geometrical moment of inertia of SMA wire, L is the distance between supports, h_0 is the initial height of laminate, ϕ is the diameter of inserted round bar, and δ_{CFRP} is the displacement of laminate.

Figure 10 shows a comparison of the recovery force of the SMA wire and the load required for the snap-through on the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminates. The recovery force of the SMA wire was calculated by using Young's modulus at 60°C (93.5 GPa) in eq.(1). In the case with no round bar, the recovery force of the SMA wire was obviously smaller than the load required for the snap-through after the displacement of 11 mm. Therefore, the snap-through may not happen. Likewise, it is impossible to cause the snap-through with a 2 mm-diameter round bar. If we insert a 3 mm-diameter round bar, the recovery force of the SMA wire exceeds the load required for the snap-through throughout the snap-through process. Namely, more than 3 mm in diameter of the round bar is required to control the snap-through. Actually, when we supplied the electric current to the system of 3 mm insert bar, the snap-through took place as expected.

A total of 10 specimens were tested and a comparison of the predicted values and the experimental results on the necessary diameter of the round bars is shown in Table 2. Two kinds of tests, Test A and Test B, were conducted to investigate the influence of the SMA wire attached on the reverse side. Test A means that no SMA wire is attached on the reverse side and Test B is the case of attaching SMA wires on both surfaces. These tests showed almost the same results. Therefore, it is possible to generate back and forth snap-through by attaching SMA wires on both surfaces. The predicted values were nearly consistent with the experimental

Fig.10 Comparison of recovery force of SMA wire and load required for snap-through, $(0^\circ/90^\circ)$ laminates.

Table 2 Comparison of predicted values and experimental results on necessary diameter of round bar.

Fig.11 Comparison of recovery force of SMA wire and load required for snap-through, $(0^\circ/90^\circ_2)$ laminates.

results. In other words, it is possible to control the snap-through of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ crossply laminates by using a single Ti-Ni shape memory alloy wire and a round bar.

Hereafter, we investigated the control for the $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ crossply laminates. Figure 11 represents the relation of the recovery force of the SMA wire and the load required for the snap-through of the $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminates. In this case, it is necessary to insert an 8 mm-diameter round bar to cause the snap-through, although we have not confirmed this by experiments. At any rate, such a system is not practicable in view of downsizing the control system of the snap-through.

To keep a compact system, a system of using a thicker SMA wire is explored. Figure 12 is the result of the simulation for the snap-through control with $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminates. By just exchanging 1 mm in diameter of the SMA wire with 1.5mm, the snap-through of $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ laminate is realized without a round bar.

So far, an electric current was applied to the SMA wire in order to raise the temperature. However, other heat sources can be used instead such as in Fig.13. That is, instead of supplying the electric current, hot air of about 60°C was blown on only the top surface. In this case, the snap-through phenomenon was also observed, although quantitative measurement was not carried out. Thus, this system can be used as a sensor (temperature) – actuator combined device.

CONCLUSIONS

The present paper addresses how to control the snap-through phenomenon of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ or $[0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2]$ crossply laminates. In this study, we were able to cause the snap-through by the aid of SMA coil straight wires and round bars, thus, such a system has a potential being a candidate for a device with the characteristics of both sensor and actuator, although it is still at the stage of a feasibility study and appropriate applications are yet to be found

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Fig.13 Automatic snap-through by hot air.

Fig.12 Simulation for snap-through control, $(0^\circ_2/90^\circ_2)$ laminate.

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